

Optical response of channel waveguides in silicate glass created via ion implantation with optical barriers of varying thickness

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ABSTRACT

Channel waveguides have been fabricated through ion implantation combined with photolithography in three types of silicate glass of diverse composition. The range of the implanted ions was different. Channel waveguide was formed by single- and multi-energy C⁺-ion implantation with different ion fluences, resulting in 1×10^{16} cm⁻². The multi-energy implantation processes were performed at energies ranging from 0.8 to 1.6 MeV to establish a 1- μ m wide barrier for the optical signal, positioned approximately 2 μ m below the sample surface. For a precise methodology, Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy (RBS) was initially employed to ascertain the composition of the photoresist mask and, in conjunction with X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis, to determine the composition of the glass prior to ion implantation. Subsequently, the dimensions of the photoresist mask, glass compositions, and the derived glass-density values were utilised for SRIM simulations of the projected range of the C⁺ ion. This led to the creation of channel waveguides and, alternatively, the standard planar waveguides. The range depth of the implanted ions (2.6 μ m) and the waveguide-formation depth calculated (3.0 μ m) using m-line spectroscopy were in good agreement. In the silicate glass with the highest Si content, the deepest range of carbon ions was SRIM-simulated, and optical modes (TE₀ and TE₁) were demonstrated at the wavelength of 473 nm. The increase in the refractive index corresponded to the value of 0.0168 for 473 nm. The effect of glass composition on the waveguide's fabrication was discussed. In addition, there was an evident difference between multi- and single-energy implantation processes. When an optical signal with the wavelength of 473 nm was introduced into the sample, only one mode was propagated for the single-energy implantation of C⁺ ions, whereas two modes were observed for the multi-energy implantation. The possibility of using multi-energy ion implantation for the controlled preparation of optical waveguides in glass has been demonstrated.

1. Introduction

Preparation of microstructures in material is widely used in fields such as photonics, telecommunications and sensing to develop complex structures that control light signals. Direct writing of optical waveguides using photons, electrons or ions is one of the key applications of glass microstructuring today [1–3]. Alternatively, ion implantation typically serves with defined depth and thickness of the layer with embedded ions, being modified by radiation defects causing optical refractive modification. By using different incident beams mainly energies, it is possible to create high refractive index regions that form an optical waveguide, where refractive index profiles (step or gradient) is crucial

for studying the properties of optical waveguides [4]. In the case, when we are using ion implantation with broad beam instead of ion beam lithography with focused beams, micrometer-sized mask can be used to created versatile structures. The geometry of the structures formed is also very important, where planar or slab waveguides constrain the propagation of light in one dimension (1D) waveguide, while channel or ridge waveguides constrain light in two dimensions (2D) waveguide [1,2]. 3D waveguides are then used to create more complex spatial structures such as optical circuits [5,6]. Currently, there are several technologies for creating optical waveguides in glass, each tailored to different performance requirements, material compatibility, and fabrication precision. It is possible to distinguish diffusion technologies

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(metal-ion diffusion [3,7], ion exchange [8,9]); growth technologies (additive manufacturing [10,11], sputtering [12], molecular-beam epitaxy [13], pulsed-laser deposition [14], chemical vapour deposition [15]; writing technologies (ultrafast laser writing [16,17], ion implantation [18]).

The ion implantation is particularly versatile, as it can be applied to a wide range of materials [19]. It has been successfully used to create waveguides in various materials, including crystals, glass and even polymers, by implanting different ions at energies ranging from several keV to several MeV [19]. In the glass substrate it has been successfully used to produce buried channel waveguides for erbium-doped integrated optical amplifiers [20]. In recent years, ion-implanted waveguides have mostly been fabricated using light ions such as hydrogen (H) and helium (He) [13,14], heavy ions such as silicon (Si), nickel (Ni), silver (Ag), copper (Cu) and gold (Au) [21–24], but also with laser-active elements such as erbium (Er) or ytterbium (Yb) [25]. In principle, there is a different mechanism of optical waveguide formation when using heavy or light ions. When light ions are implanted, the nuclear collisions during implantation cause damage, reducing the physical density of the substrate. This creates a low-density buried region that has a refractive index lower than that of the substrate and acts as an optical barrier. The region between the surface and the optical barrier has a higher refractive index and can function as a waveguide [26]. In contrast, heavy ions can increase the density, polarizability, or structural characteristics of the substrate, resulting in an increased refractive index in the implanted region. This region is surrounded by regions with a lower refractive index, forming a typical optical waveguide [27]. It has been shown that heavier-ion-implanted waveguides can be fabricated more efficiently due to the lower ion fluence (10^{14} – 10^{15} ions/cm²) relative to light-ion-implanted one (10^{16} – 10^{17} ions/cm²) [28,29]. However, optical waveguides fabricated by ion implantation in silicate glasses, which have a large refractive index change, may exhibit high propagation losses ~ 15 dB/cm [30,31]. The thermal annealing [32] is most commonly used to improve the optical performance of all the ion-implanted waveguides fabricated by the technique of ion implantation, reducing both the frequency of colour centres and propagation loss. Using post-implantation annealing, optical waveguides can achieve optical loss values of around 0.4 dB/cm@633 nm in silicate glasses [33] or even as low as 0.37 dB/cm@633 nm in fused silica [34,35]. These values are acceptable for practical application in photonics.

If we focus on the structural changes in the glass caused during ion implantation, it is evident a significant disruption to the glass network, particularly at the projected depth or the region where the implanted particles pass through the glass structure. In silicate glass, the network composed of (SiO₄)⁰ tetrahedra, which are only connected at the corners and not through the edges or faces, is disrupted [36,37]. The presence of alkali ions such as Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺ in silica glass leads to the breaking of the Si-O-Si linkage and the formation of Si-O- terminations. This depolymerises the glass structure, and the alkali ions become relatively mobile within the structure. Through a diffusion mechanism, they can migrate to regions with defects or reach the region where the implanted ions are located. Various types of borosilicate glass are commonly used in visible and near-infrared photonics. They replace the silicon and oxygen network with (BO_{3/2}) or (BO_{4/2})⁻ units, depending on the boron content. The relationship between these units is not yet fully understood. BK7, a type of borosilicate glass, is known for its high homogeneity, low presence of bubbles and inclusions, and ease of manufacturing. It is a popular choice for transmissivity optics, with a transmission range of 380–2100 nm.

New research on the preparation of optical waveguides by ion implantation focuses on expanding the optical barrier or creating the waveguide core directly through multi-energy ion implantation [38,39]. Multi-energy ion implantation is employed to achieve different penetration depths and distribution widths. This technique results in thicker layers, which exhibit lower propagation losses and a better overlap between the guided mode and the implanted region. In comparison with

the waveguides produced by a single energy ion implantation process at a specific energy, thicker waveguides enable more efficient input coupling [40,41]. The guiding structures can be precisely controlled by adjusting the species, energies and fluences of the implanted ions. The optical waveguide with an optical barrier prepared by multi-energy ion implantation can be formed in fused-silica glass [42,43] or rarely in silicate glass [44,45]. Other glass substrates where ion implantation has been applied include fluoride, germanite and soda-lime glass [46].

This paper presents a new approach and aim to get new data from fabrication of channel waveguides by combining photolithography and single- and multi-energy implantation of C⁺ ions (referred to as “C ions” in this paper). Using different ion implantation fluences and energies, channel waveguides with wide barriers were fabricated, which ensured high reproducibility of channel waveguides on different silicate glass substrates. The broad beam of carbon ions was used to create microstructures in glasses via mask. The reason is, that in photolithography the focusing of the beam would be limited by energy, in case of mask we can use broader ion energy range and ion fluence range. Additionally, glass network can play crucial role in defect creation and implanted specie dissipation, thus can influence final waveguide size, quality and optical properties [47,48]. Thus, three different glasses with various structure network, connected to concentration of glass network-formers as well modifiers, were chosen. The aim was to investigate the optical response of different structural silicate glass networks and to demonstrate the versatility of the chosen technology. Lower ion implantation energies possess by narrower depth statistical distribution of implanted carbon ions due to less straggling during the ion trajectory, thus narrower implanted layer is created.

2. Experimental setup

2.1. Glass substrates

Based on our previous work [49], three different types of glass have been used to study waveguide fabrication by the ion-implantation technique. The first of them was the reference optical glass **S-1** with a high SiO₂ content (consisting mainly silicate network). The glass **GIL11** had an aluminium-silicate network with a relatively high content of lithium ions as glass modifier. The **BK7** glass is a common optical glass prepared to achieve the value of the refractive index; its network is borosilicate, and the glass contains potassium, sodium and barium as network modifiers. Two of these glass types, **GIL11** and **S-1**, were prepared using a standard melting process, which had been designed to achieve the best optical homogeneity. The melting process took place in a Pt crucible in a classic glass furnace. The samples of the prepared glass were cut into pieces with dimensions of approximately 30 × 30 × 1 mm and polished on both sides to optical quality using a suspension of cerium dioxide. The third type of glass of good optical quality, **BK7**, was supplied by the Glass Research Institute in Hradec Králové. This glass was also 30 × 30 × 0.7 mm and was polished on one side. The composition of the glass was verified by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) method (the results are shown below). The glass-density values were determined pycnometrically each time as the average of three measurements; the individual-glass values are as follows: **S-1** – 2.242 ± 0.005 g.cm⁻³, **GIL 11** – 2.370 ± 0.005 g.cm⁻³, **BK7** – 2.706 ± 0.005 g.cm⁻³.

2.2. Lamellar-pattern transfer by photolithography

Before deposition, the glass substrates were cleaned with acetone (10 ml at 1000 RPM) and isopropyl alcohol (20 ml at 1000 RPM) on a Labclaster LabSpin 8 coater (SUSS Microtec SE). The negative photoresist AR-N 4340 (Allresist GmbH) was deposited by spin coating on a Labclaster LabSpin 8 coater with the following spin parameters: the rotation speed of 1000 RPM, the acceleration of 500 RPM, and the spin time of 60 s for the final thickness of the approximate photoresist (*h*) 2.8

$\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ (the thickness of the layer was determined by RBS method as well as accuracy was measured in five different place of the sample – see subchapter 2.4). The substrates were immediately soft baked on a Labclaster Hot Plate HP8 at 90°C for 90 s and then relaxed for 5 min. A lamellar pattern in the overall spread 1.5 cm was prepared in the KLayout viewer and editor. The substrates were UV-exposed on a Micro Writer ML3 Baby Plus direct laser writer (Durham Magneto Optics) equipped with 385 nm semiconductor light source. Optical microscope with $3\times$ aspheric objective lens and $10\times$ plan achromatic objective lens (Olympus) with the $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ resolution mode was used. The substrates were immediately post-exposure baked on the Labclaster Hot Plate HP8 at 95°C for 150 s and then relaxed for 5 min. The immersion technique was used for resist development. The developer AR-300–26 (Allresist GmbH) was prepared in a 1:2 (V/V) solution with distilled water (dH_2O) in one Petri dish and 1:3 (V/V) with dH_2O in another Petri dish. The substrates were then immersed in the first Petri dish for 1 min and the second one for 30 s. The removed substrates were immediately immersed in the beaker containing dH_2O and blow-dried with a nitrogen stream.

The final structures in photoresist were hardened by flood exposure on an MA/BA Gen4 mask aligner by the exposition dose of $150 \text{ mJ}/\text{cm}^2$ and hard baked on the Labclaster Hot Plate HP8 at 115°C for 1 min. Fig. 1 shows the lamellar pattern prepared by photolithography on S-1 (a), GIL11 (b), and BK7 (c) displayed using digital microscopy. From these images the parameters of the lamellar pattern are obvious, such as thickness (t) of $16.5 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$ and a gap (w) of $9.3 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ for S-1 ($t =$

$14.5 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ and a $w = 11.9 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$ for GIL11; $t = 8.9 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ and $w = 18.0 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ for BK7). The accuracy of the thickness was obtained by repeatedly measuring the thickness in ten different places.

2.3. Simulation and ion implantation

The Monte Carlo (MC) simulation code Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM-2013) [50] was used to simulate the projected range of C ions in the photoresist AR-N 4340. To produce the waveguide, the projected range of the C ion must be lower than the thickness of the photoresist itself (below $2.8 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$). The energies required for C ion implantation were selected accordingly the photoresist thickness. In addition, SRIM simulation makes it possible to calculate nuclear and electronic stopping power as a function of penetration depth.

The simulated profiles for 0.8 and 1.6 MeV C ions are shown in Fig. 2a–c for S-1, GIL11 and BK7, respectively. We can see that the electronic damage takes place mainly during the trajectory of incident ions, generating colour centres and near-surface damage, whereas the nuclear damage of the glasses is concentrated at the end of the C-ion track. The peak (maximum value) of the nuclear energy deposition is located at the depth of ~ 1.4 and $2.3 \mu\text{m}$ for S-1 implanted using 0.8 and 1.6 MeV C ions, respectively. In the case of GIL11 and BK7 types of glass, because of their higher density, the peak is in a smaller depth, but the character of the nuclear and electronic damage is quite similar.

For a simulation performed for multi-energy implantation, the resulting depth profile of the implanted ion range is shown in Fig. 3. It is

Fig. 1. An optical micrograph from the Optika digital microscopes DM of the lamellar pattern prepared by photolithography before ion implantation on S-1 (a), GIL11 (c), and BK7 (e) (left column). The right column shows a zoom of the lamellar pattern in rectangle for S-1 (b), GIL11 (d), and BK7 (f).

Fig. 2. Nuclear and electronic stopping power as a function of penetration depth for 0.8 MeV and 1.6 MeV C ions implanted in S-1 (a), GIL11 (b) and BK7 (c) calculated by the SRIM code.

Fig. 3. A simulation of multi-energy implantations towards the fabrication of a step-index waveguide in BK7.

obvious from the simulation that ion-implantation processes at different ion fluences were performed to produce broad waveguides fabricated by C-ion implantation at the energies of 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4 and 1.6 MeV. The C-ion depth profiles in the different types of glass were calculated using SRIM-code simulations for the 10,000 incident ions. These profiles were used for the fitting procedure that are necessary for ion-fluence

calculation.

The profiles (p_i) were then summed with the corresponding weights (w_i):

$$p = w_1p_1 + w_2p_2 + w_3p_3 + w_4p_4 + w_5p_5 \quad (1)$$

The weights were determined by fitting the flat top of the profile p to the horizontal line (the function $\chi^2 = \sum_n (2000 - p(d_n))^2$ was minimised for the histogram bins in the interval $d_n = [1.2\mu\text{m}, 1.8\mu\text{m}]$. The best ‘flat-top’ profile was obtained with the weights: 0.8, 0.9... 1.0. The SRIM-calculated profiles and their weighted sum are shown in Fig. 3.

From the fitting procedure, we have deduced the required ion-implantation fluence for each energy and each glass. A similar approach can be found in [51]. The respective implantation fluences are summarised in Table 1 for S-1, GIL11 and BK7 and the implantation energies of 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4 and 1.6 MeV.

Table 1

The calculated implantation fluences using equation (1) that have been used for C-ion implantation into the glass S-1, GIL11 and BK7 at the energies of 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4 and 1.6 MeV.

Implantation energy [MeV]	Fluences [$\times 10^{16}$ ions/cm ²]		
	S-1	GIL11	BK7
0.8	0.21	0.22	0.22
1.0	0.20	0.20	0.19
1.2	0.18	0.18	0.19
1.4	0.16	0.16	0.17
1.6	0.25	0.25	0.23

For all the simulations mentioned above, the following input parameters and standards were used: i) calculation with fully damaged cascades, with the lattice binding energy set to zero; ii) the default SRIM surface binding energy; iii) the displacement energies (E_d) of each glass based on internationally recommended standard values, mentioned in [52–55], iv) 10,000 incident ions to achieve consistent statistics within low uncertainty.

After lamellar-pattern preparation in photoresist functioning as a mask, the glass samples covered with this mask were implanted with C ions. Single-energy (1.0 MeV) and multi-energy (from 0.8 MeV to 1.6 MeV) C implantation with the total fluence in the order of 10^{16} cm^{-2} were performed using the Tandetron 4130 MC electrostatic accelerator at the Nuclear Physics Institute in Řež near Prague (Czech Republic). The scheme of the implantation process through the lamellar pattern from photoresist on the surface of the glass and the corresponding dimensions are shown in Fig. 4. In the region where the lamella is located, the C ions are blocked and accumulate inside the photoresist lamella, preventing them from further penetration. In areas without lamellae (channels), the ions pass through and penetrate the sample. This creates an optical barrier within the range of the implanted particles (Fig. 4a). Afterward, the photoresist is then removed from the sample. The channel area after the penetration and range of the ions can be seen in the electron microscope image in Fig. 4b. The ion beam was scanned during the implantation experiment to guarantee uniform implantation over the glass. A stable working pressure (below $6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}$) was guaranteed by a pumping system with a turbomolecular pump. A high vacuum and load-lock system were employed to position the samples in the implantation chamber with the aim to minimise sample contamination resulting from residual hydrocarbons. The experiment was preceded by intensive pumping, lasting for 24 h.

Additionally, standard samples, devoid of a mask on their surfaces, were prepared under identical ion-implantation conditions, i.e. one set by single-energy (1.0 MeV) and second set of samples by multi-energy (from 0.8 MeV to 1.6 MeV) C implantation with the total fluence in the order of 10^{16} cm^{-2} . That means, the ion beam scanned the glass surface of the sample during implantation and a planar waveguide was formed. These samples were primarily utilised as the reference samples for the measurement of refractive index changes, absorption spectra as well as waveguides properties by m-line spectroscopy. After implantation, all samples were thermally treated at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h in a vacuum to partially mitigate the production of defects and colour centres.

Fig. 4. (a) A scheme of the channel waveguide preparation using C-ion implantation through a lamellar-patterned mask prepared by photolithography. The final thickness of the photoresist (h) is $2.8 \pm 0.1 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$. The lamellar pattern has been prepared with the thickness (t) of $16.5 \pm 0.4 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ and a gap (channel size) (w) of $9.3 \pm 0.5 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ for S-1 (the thickness of $14.5 \pm 0.2 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ and a gap $11.9 \pm 0.4 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ for GIL11; the thickness of $8.9 \pm 0.3 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ and a gap of $18.0 \pm 0.3 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ for BK7). (b) SEM image in inset shows prepared optical waveguide in GIL11 after photoresist removal.

2.4. Analytical methods

Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS) was used to determine the thickness of the photoresist AR-N 4340 and the concentration of glass before and after C-ion implantation. The RBS measurement was performed using 2-MeV $^4\text{He}^+$ ions in Rutherford back-scattering mode; and non-RBS analysis offering high back-scattering cross section of ions on carbon was provided using beam of 1.74-MeV H^+ ions. The resonant cross section for light elements is significantly increased in the case of the proton beam used. A surface-barrier Si detector with a circular aperture of 5.4 mm in diameter was placed at 70 mm from the sample holder at the scattering angle of 170° . The energy resolution of the detector was about 20 keV. Further, the RBS measurement was used to monitor the composition of all the prepared glass samples before C-ion implantation using 2-MeV $^4\text{He}^+$ ions. The ion currents utilised during the RBS analysis were $\sim 5 \text{ nA}$. The RBS spectra were evaluated by the SIMNRA code [56] to provide quantitative analysis.

An AVANTES AvaSpec Starline spectrometer was used to measure absorption spectra in the range of 250–1100 nm. The optical fibre was approached to the sample at 0.1 mm and the light was passed perpendicularly through the prepared optical layer. Moreover, the absorbance values at 1300 and 1550 nm were verified on a Lambda 1050 + 3D absorption spectrometer.

The m-line spectroscopy using the Metricon model 2010/M prism coupler was utilised for the measurement of the effective refractive indices (n_{eff}) of the pristine-glass substrates and waveguiding properties of the planar structure without masking (e.i. number of modes, waveguide-formation depth and refractive index changes). The principle of the Metricon measurement setup has already been presented in [57,58]. The beam of light coming from a laser source is coupled into measured samples using the prism. The beam of light reaches the base of the coupling prism and is reflected into a germanium photodetector. The measured C-implanted waveguide, as well as the coupling prism and the germanium photodetector are mounted on a rotatory table. This arrangement makes it possible to change the angle of incidence and the angle of the laser beam as required. The angles of incidence correspond to the sharp drop reflectivity peaks that occur in the spectrum and correspond to the excitation of guided modes. At the coupling angles (θ), the light is coupled into the waveguide via a coupling prism, which results in the lack of reflected light at the base of the prism, consequently forming the dark-mode-line spectrum. From the positions of the angles of incidence, it is then possible to determine the n_{eff} of the mode and the refractive index of the waveguide. The measurements were performed at five wavelengths (473, 633, 964, 1311 and 1552 nm) using a set for transverse-electric (TE) polarisation. The prism #200-P-4a with the refractive index $n = 2.1558$ ($\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$) was applied, and the effective refractive n_{eff} indices of the prism ranged from 1.2 to 2.02 at the wavelength $\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$. In direct measurements, at low wavelengths, a maximally of two guided optical modes could always be measured and assigned n_{eff} values. However, the Wentzel-Krammer-Brillouin (WKB) [59] approximation could not be used to reconstruct the refractive index profile due to the small number of modes.

3. Results

The RBS spectra from pristine-glass samples are shown in Fig. 5. The SIMNRA simulations are depicted with elemental composition.

The elemental composition of pristine-glass samples before implantation was determined using two methods RBS and XRF. In RBS were used He-ion beam with 2 MeV. A comparison of the determination results obtained by RBS and XRF is shown in Table 2. The trends in composition between the different types of glass are in good agreement. The XRF method does not allow the determination of the lithium content, which has been added to the total elemental mass and very probably partially leached from the melt during glass melting. Therefore, its content is different from the content of the other elements determined

Fig. 5. The RBS experimental (red lines, measured using 2-MeV He) and SIMNRA simulation (sum: black lines, elements: other-colour lines) spectra for pristine-glass samples S-1 (a), GIL11 (b) and BK7 (c), respectively. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 2

The composition (at. %) of the glasses used for optical-waveguide preparation. The compositions have been determined from RBS and XRF measurements.

		Concentration [at. %]										Others
		Si	O	Na	Al	K	B	Zn	Ca	Fe	Li	
RBS	S-1	31	66.0	2	0.8	–	–	–	–	0.2	–	
	GIL11	28.0	64.5	0.7	4.1	–	–	–	–	–	2.5	As
	BK7	20	59.8	6	2	3	7	0.2	–	–	–	Ba
XRF	S-1	31	65	3	1	–	–	–	–	–	–	Fe
	GIL11	20	56	2	7	–	–	–	–	–	13	
	BK7	22	60	6	–	5	7	–	–	–	–	Al, Zn, Ba

by the RBS method and more accurate.

After C-ion implantation, it was necessary to measure RBS spectra at different energies to increase the sensitivity on implanted carbon. The RBS spectra from pristine-glass samples and samples implanted with single-energy C ions measured using 1.74-MeV H ions are shown in Fig. 6a, 6b and 6c for S-1, GIL11 and BK7, respectively. The SIMNRA simulations are not shown for clarity. It is evident that after C-ion implantation, the content of oxygen is reduced. The C concentration–depth profiles have been extracted from RBS spectra and the results from the C concentration–depth profiles have been compared to the simulation in the SRIM code (see Table 3). For multi-energetic ion implantation, RBS measurement is not possible because it exceeds the depth range of the method.

The RBS method was chosen for the precise determination of the silicate-glass composition and to confirm that after C ion implantation, the delivered carbon ion total fluence agrees with experiment and simultaneously we can see the difference in various glass matrices, where S-1 exhibited highest oxygen depletion in the implanted layer.

The determined compositions of glasses were afterwards used to simulate the projected ranges of C ions in the glass samples with the higher accuracy. The projected ranges and standard deviations ($R_p \pm \Delta R_p$) of 0.8–1.6-MeV C from the SRIM simulation is shown in Table 3 for S-1, GIL11 and BK7, respectively. The carbon depth profiles extracted from RBS for single-energy C-ion implantation are also shown in the insert.

Table 3 shows that with the increasing energy of C ions, the R_p in S-1 increases too, from $1.51 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{m}$ to $2.29 \pm 0.17 \mu\text{m}$. A similar trend is evident for GIL11 as well as BK7. The maximum values of R_p and ΔR_p have been observed in S-1.

The optical absorption spectra of the pristine glass substrate together with the spectra of the samples implanted with C ions at energies of 1 MeV and 0.8–1.6 MeV are shown in Fig. 7 for the range 250–1100 nm. In addition, low absorbance values for higher wavelengths (1100–1600 nm range) were also verified for all samples. Since it was practically no different from the value at 1000 nm, it was not shown in Fig. 7. Among the substrates tested, the highest absorption values were recorded for the BK7 glass. This can be attributed to the fact that the BK7 sample was

Fig. 6. The RBS experimental spectra (black lines: pristine, blue lines: single-energy C-ion implantation, red lines: multi-energy C-ion implantation) of **S-1** (a), **GIL11** (c) and **BK7** (e) measured using 1.74-MeV H. The C concentration–depth profiles have been extracted from RBS spectra (right column). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Table 3

C-ion projected ranges and standard deviations ($R_p \pm \Delta R_p$) in the glass substrates **S-1**, **GIL11** and **BK7** determined using the SRIM simulation for various energies and a comparison with the experimental values measured for the energy of 1.0 MeV.

Energy [MeV]	SRIM $R_p \pm \Delta R$ [μm]					Experiment $R_p \pm \Delta R$ [μm]
	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.4	1.6	
S-1	1.51 ± 0.15	1.73 ± 0.15	1.92 ± 0.16	2.11 ± 0.17	2.29 ± 0.17	1.68 ± 0.2
	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.17	0.17	
GIL11	1.42 ± 0.14	1.62 ± 0.14	1.80 ± 0.15	1.98 ± 0.16	2.15 ± 0.16	1.60 ± 0.2
	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.16	0.16	
BK7	1.25 ± 0.13	1.43 ± 0.13	1.60 ± 0.14	1.75 ± 0.14	1.90 ± 0.14	1.45 ± 0.2
	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.14	0.14	

only polished on one side, which likely contributed to higher absorption. The increase in absorption intensity due to C-ion implantation was mostly pronounced in the **BK7** and **GIL11** glasses, where a noticeable shift in the absorption edge was also observed. Specifically, in the **BK7** glass, C-ion implantation resulted in 7 % of the shift, as depicted in Fig. 7c. In contrast, the **S-1** glass (Fig. 7a) exhibited only a slight increase in absorption, which did not exceed 2 %. This indicates that the effect of ion implantation on absorption varies significantly depending on the type of glass.

The dispersion curve as a dependence of the n_{eff} on the wavelength of

the pristine-glass substrates and the waveguide properties of the prepared layers were measured by m-line spectroscopy at five wavelengths (473, 633, 964, 1311 and 1552 nm). Fig. 8 shows the refractive-intensity curves for all three glass substrates. The measurement of the pristine-glass substrates at 633 nm (black curve) is used as the standard. The sharp edge corresponds to the decrease of intensity after the optical signal is introduced into the substrate and the inscribed value represents the n_{eff} of the substrate. For the sake of clarity, the measurements of the substrate n_{eff} at other wavelengths are not included, nevertheless the values are shown in Table 4.

The refractive index values of the pristine glass substrates were in line with our assumptions. The glass **S-1**, with the highest content of silicate network, showed the lowest density as well the lowest refractive index, whereas the glass **BK7**, containing Ba^{2+} ions as a modifier, exhibited the highest density, corresponding to the highest value of the refractive index.

The other curves in Fig. 8 (multi-coloured) correspond to the propagation of light in the layers prepared by ion implantation in various glass substrates when a signal of a different wavelength is introduced. The presence of distinct peaks in the region before the edge of the intensity drop corresponds to the propagation of the individual optical modes (labelled TE_0 and TE_1). The small intensity drops in the region of the edge or behind it (indicated by black arrows) then corresponds to some interference, indicating surface modification and some seeds of future modes of light.

If we focused on the changes of refractive index values, the sharp edge on the colour curves should always correspond to the n_{eff} value of

Fig. 7. The absorption spectra in the range of 250–1100 nm for the pristine-glass substrate (black line) and the sample implanted with a 1-MeV C (blue lines) and 0.8–1.6-MeV C (red lines) – the spectra were acquired in the region of the channel waveguides – **S1** (a), **GIL11** (b) and **BK7** (c). In the inset is shown zoom of the narrow region from 260–400 nm for better clarity. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

pristine glass at a given wavelength. Thus, the n_{eff} values corresponding to these sharp were plotted into Table 4 together with Δn_{eff} (i.e. difference from the refractive index value of pristine glass) and compared them for single- and multi-energy implantation and different wavelengths. First, the difference between the substrate types is clear from the values in Table 4. In **S-1** glass, we generally observed the smallest differences, whereas in **BK7** glass the sharp was not nearly as sharp and thus the n_{eff} values had larger differences. Moreover, a positive change (increase of n_{eff}) occurs in the **S-1** glass. On the other hand, the n_{eff} tends to decrease for the **BK7** and **GIL11** glass samples. Furthermore, it is possible to observe the effect of wavelength, where with increasing wavelength the differences for all substrates are smaller or even zero. This is consistent with the fact that an optical signal with a small wavelength responds better to changes in the material than a signal with a larger wavelength. The effect of the multi-energy to single-energy implantation differs in various glass substrates. Multi-energy implantation has been shown to

modify the n_{eff} value in the **S-1** glass to a greater extent. On the other hand, a very small change in n_{eff} was shown in glass **BK7** glass. The described results correspond well to the creation of an optical waveguide film (see below) in **S-1** glass and to the mere modification of the surface of the other substrates.

If we focus on the waveguiding properties of the films, the optical modes are significant in Fig. 8a and b in the **S-1** glass, where the range of the carbon ions is expected to be the deepest and hence the layer is the widest. What is also obvious is the difference between multi- and single-energy implantation (see (a) and (b)), where at 473 nm only one mode of

light propagates for single-energy C-ion implantation and two modes for multi-energy implantation.

Using dispersion equation [60] the refractive index value was determined. If two or more modes were propagating through the waveguide, the refractive index corresponding to individual modes could be calculated. The value of the refractive index corresponding to each mode is higher than the value of the n_{eff} of the substrate; for the wavelength of 473 nm in the **S-1** glass (multi-energy implantation), the calculated change of refractive index is + 0.0168. The layer depth estimated by calculation from the two-mode (**S-1** at 473 nm) spectrum is 3.0091 μm , which is in reasonably good agreement with the range of the implanted ions. For waveguides propagating only one optical mode, the surface refractive index was calculated using an estimation of the layer thickness (1 μm for single-energy implantation and 3 μm for multi-energy implantation). The determined value was for the wavelength of 633 nm in the **S-1** glass (multi-energy implantation) + 0.0256, for the wavelength of 473 nm in the **S-1** glass (single-energy implantation) + 0.0051 and for the wavelength of 633 nm in the **S-1** glass (multi-energy implantation) + 0.0060. In the other two types of glass, i.e. the glass **GIL11** (Fig. 8c and d) and **BK7** (Fig. 8e and f), either smaller or zero number of modes is observed even at low wavelengths. From the shape of the peak one would suspect a different character of the optical modes (see, for example, the peaks marked with an arrow in **BK7** glass in Fig. 8e and 8f), which corresponds to the dual layer character. The trend evident from these two pictures is in good agreement with the predicted depth of the projected range of carbon (see Table 3) and is consistent with the indicated difference between multi-energy and single-energy

Fig. 8. The relative intensity of the TE-polarised light reflected from the prism as a function of the effective refractive index at the different wavelengths for single- and multi-energy ion implantations into the S-1 (a,b), GIL11 (c,d) and BK7 glass (e,f).

implantation.

4. Discussion

During C ion implantation, the optical waveguides are created by local structural modification of the glass substrate. The depth and thickness of the damaged layer are determined by the ion-implantation energy and fluence, respectively. According to the literature [61], where protons and carbon have been implanted into Nd:YAG, the ion implantation of the C ions leads to a defect accumulation in the irradiated layers and thus to a change in the refractive index. The literature [62,63]

explains this change in two ways – as the creation of the so-called ‘barrier waveguide’ and as the creation of two layers, where one layer is created by the penetration of the implanted particle (close to the sample surface) and the other layer by the impact of the implanted particle (at a certain depth). The waveguide modes are confined between the buried layer and the surface [61].

From our point of view, the damage induced in the glass samples by ion implantation has played an important role in the formation of waveguides, because it has significantly changed the glass structure and subsequently the refractive indices of most materials. The energetic ion-implantation processes result in two different types of damage, which

Table 4

Refractive index values corresponding to the sharp edge determined for different wavelengths and various glass substrates implanted with single- and multi-energy implantation of C-ions. Missing values (labelled*) were not determined because the measured intensity did not show a noticeable edge. Therefore, the method was able to detect n_{eff} even after changing the input signal intensity.

S-1					
Wavelength [nm]	n_{eff} Pristine glass	n_{eff} Single energy	Δn_{eff}	n_{eff} Multi-energy	Δn_{eff}
473	1.4800	1.4789	-0.0011	1.4846	+0.0046
633	1.4721	1.4712	-0.0009	1.476	+0.0039
964	1.4655	1.4657	+0.0002	1.4675	+0.0020
1311	1.4611	1.4604	-0.0007	1.4613	+0.0002
1552	1.4579	*		1.4579	0.0000
GIL11					
Wavelength [nm]	n_{eff} Pristine glass	n_{eff} Single energy	Δn_{eff}	n_{eff} Multi-energy	Δn_{eff}
473	1.5333	1.5311	-0.0022	1.5261	-0.0072
633	1.5245	1.5211	-0.0034	1.5234	-0.0011
964	1.5173	*		*	
1311	1.5127	1.5097	-0.003	1.5046	-0.0081
1552	1.5097	*		*	
BK7					
Wavelength [nm]	n_{eff} Pristine glass	n_{eff} Single energy	Δn_{eff}	n_{eff} Multi-energy	Δn_{eff}
473	1.5387	1.5166	-0.0221	1.5321	-0.0066
633	1.5295	1.5075	-0.0220	1.5234	-0.0061
964	1.522	*		1.5166	-0.0054
1311	1.5178	1.5042	-0.0136	1.5178	0.0000
1552	1.5145	1.4997	-0.0148	1.5147	+0.0002

are dominated by two modes, i.e. electronic ionisation and the nuclear-collision cascade. The former is caused by the electronic stopping power and the latter one results from the nuclear stopping power. Given the dual mechanism of structural damage, the question is how the waveguide is formed. From our experiments, it is evident in single-energy implantation, when the barrier width is narrower and the optical waveguide carries fewer modes. Electronic stopping, as it was shown by SRIM simulation, is significantly prevailing in the surface layer, instead of it, the nuclear stopping via collisions and defect creation is playing role at the end of ion path, where one single maximum of damage due to single energy of ions is created. In the case of multi-energy implantation, the barrier widens significantly due to the sum of several maxima of nuclear stopping due to the multi-energetic ion beams used, and the waveguide had more modes. We thus assume that light propagates between the surface and the barrier, and its properties can be influenced by the barrier width. Therefore, the optical barrier and the resulting waveguide could be an outcome of the damage caused by the nuclear stopping of the implanted carbon ions at the end of the individual paths for each ion energy, where the density and refractive index are reduced. Such an assumption is consistent with the results reported in the literature [19,64]. Comparing the effect of the glass composition on the waveguide fabrication during ion implantation, the difference between the silicate network glass (S-1) and the other two types of glass is clear. It is shown that after the ion implantation, the refractive index of S-1 glass increases and the waveguides are formed, whereas the other glasses tend to have the same or lower refractive index value, and no waveguide is formed. The question remains whether waveguides could be formed in these glasses using increase the ion implantation energy. According to our previous work [49], the mechanism of refractive index enhancement could be as follows: the drift of a particle through the silicate covalent network leads to bond breaking (reduction of the degree of crosslinking) and the formation of non-bridging oxygen (was verified by Raman spectroscopy), which cause a polarizability increase and therefore also the increase of refractive index value [65]. In a less covalent type of glass containing a more complex glass network or ion-bonded glass modifiers, the particle impact causes the same damage as in pure silicate glass, but the loosened structure can compensate for the defects more easily. Due

to the presence of modifiers that compensate for the charges on the terminal oxygen will not cause such a large change in polarizability and the refractive index will not increase. This could be the reason for the easier formation of a barrier waveguide in glass having a silicate structural network.

5. Conclusion

In this study, optical waveguides were fabricated in various silicate glass substrates using single- and multi-energy C-ion implantation combined with photolithography. The projected range, i.e., also the corresponding waveguide depth, was controlled by the composition of the glass substrate used and the selected ion implantation conditions. The properties of the formed barrier waveguides, i.e., the optical signal propagation, can be controlled by the width of the implanted region during multi-energy implantation. The results show that the waveguides are easier to form in high silica glass. In glasses containing other crosslinking agents or glass modifiers, a waveguide formed under the same experimental conditions always propagates a lower number of optical modes. In this way, the attractive technique of writing waveguides by ion beam of light elements through a lithographic mask has been shown to be effectively used to fabricate optical waveguides with precise geometry. This unique technique allows the creation of waveguide channels in different types of materials with a high degree of reproducibility. Even though we have so far demonstrated the preparation of shallow waveguides leading signal of shorter wavelengths (473 and 633 nm), the methodology described in this study offers remarkable flexibility. By adjusting the implantation parameters (especially the energy), the technique can be adapted to form channel waveguides at larger predefined depths, indicating the potential for tailoring the waveguide properties to specific applications. The results show that this approach is highly efficient, versatile and offers precise control over the fabrication of waveguides, making it a suitable method for fabricating channel waveguides in silicate glasses.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Romana Mikšová: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Pavla Někviňová:** Optical analysis, m-line spectroscopy, Writing. **Petr Aubrecht:** Lamellar-pattern transfer by photolithography. **Anna Macková:** Simulation, Writing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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